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USE OF THE BEE-BOT ROBOT IN EDUCATIONAL PRACTICE IN PRESCHOOL INSTITUTIONS IN SERBIA

Ivan Tomic¹ & Katarina Tomic²

Academy of Applied Preschool Teaching and Health Studies

Abstract

In contemporary preschool education, increasing importance is given to the integration of digital technologies into educational practice, particularly in fostering early development of logical thinking, problem-solving skills, and basic programming concepts. One of the tools increasingly used in this context is the Bee-Bot educational robot, which enables children to learn fundamental principles of sequencing and algorithmic thinking through play. The introduction of digital tools in preschool institutions also requires examining teachers' attitudes and experiences regarding their pedagogical value, as well as the challenges and limitations of their implementation in work with preschool children. The aim of this study was to examine the extent and manner in which preschool teachers in Serbia use Bee-Bot in their work with children, as well as to identify the areas of child development most influenced by its application. Specific objectives included examining the frequency of use, teachers' competence levels, and perceptions of its pedagogical effects. The research was conducted using a quantitative approach and a survey method. The research instrument was a questionnaire designed for the purposes of this study and distributed via Google Forms. The sample consisted of 100 preschool teachers from different regions of Serbia, selected through random sampling. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and appropriate inferential methods. The results show that preschool teachers recognize the importance of using the Bee-Bot robot in educational practice, particularly in the development of cognitive abilities, logical thinking, and cooperation among children. A moderate level of self-perceived digital competence was reported ($M=3.4$; $SD=1.35$), with a high standard deviation indicating substantial individual differences among respondents. A statistically significant difference was found in the frequency of Bee-Bot use between teachers who had attended training and those who had not (Mann-Whitney $U=602.00$, $p<.001$), with trained teachers using the tool significantly more often. Respondents indicated that Bee-Bot contributes most to the development of spatial orientation (56%), followed by logical thinking (48%) and mathematical concept acquisition (40%). The main barriers to more frequent use were an insufficient number of robots and mats (34%), lack of time during the workday (33%), and the need for additional professional training (23%), while other factors were less represented (1–3%). The findings suggest the need for improved professional development of preschool teachers and more systematic integration of digital tools into the preschool curriculum.

Keywords: Bee-Bot, preschool education, digital technologies, preschool teachers, early development, algorithmic thinking

¹ itomic@vaspks.edu.rs, Krusevac, Serbia

² katarinat@vaspks.edu.rs, Krusevac, Serbia

Introduction

Contemporary educational paradigms increasingly emphasize the importance of early development of 21st-century skills, with digital competencies and computational thinking identified as key pillars of modern literacy (Chatzopoulos et al., 2021; Papadakis & Kalogiannakis, 2020). Computational thinking is defined as a focused approach to problem-solving that encompasses cognitive processes involving abstraction, decomposition, algorithmic design, evaluation, and generalization (Selby & Woollard, 2013). Although the literature presents ongoing discussions regarding its precise definition, Jeannette Wing described computational thinking as the thought processes involved in formulating problems and their solutions in such a way that the solutions are represented in a form that can be effectively carried out by an information-processing agent (Wing, 2006).

Educational robots, precisely as information-processing agents, represent an important tool for fostering computational thinking in children, as they enable learning through active exploration, problem-solving, and direct experience. By programming robots, children develop logical and sequential thinking, the ability to plan steps, identify patterns, and solve problems, all of which constitute core components of computational thinking. Through activities involving educational robots, abstract concepts become more concrete and comprehensible, as children can immediately observe the consequences of their instructions and correct errors through experimentation and trial-and-error learning. In this context, educational robotics (ER) emerges as an innovative pedagogical approach that transforms the learning process into play, enabling preschool children to explore complex concepts through the direct manipulation of tangible technological tools (Chaldi & Mantzanidou, 2021).

The integration of robotics into early childhood education is most commonly implemented through the STEAM approach (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, and Mathematics), which promotes the holistic development of the child and prepares them for solving real-world problems (Foti, 2021). The theoretical foundation of educational robotics is deeply rooted in Jean Piaget's constructivism and Seymour Papert's constructionism. According to the constructivist perspective, learning is an active process in which children construct knowledge through experience and the resolution of authentic problems (Papadakis, 2020). Papert's constructionism further extends this idea by emphasizing that the most effective learning occurs when children are engaged in creating tangible artifacts that hold personal meaning, such as programming a robot's movement in space. As physical objects, robots make abstract programming concepts less intimidating and more accessible, enabling children to observe the immediate outcomes of their cognitive efforts (Zemzami & Zbat, 2025).

The Educational and Developmental Role of the Bee-Bot Robot

The significance of educational robotics in early childhood extends beyond mere familiarization with technology and focuses on the development of cognitive, social, and motor skills through play and exploration. The implementation of tools such as Bee-Bot enables children to transition from passive consumers to active creators of digital content. Owing to its intuitive design and simple button-based interface, the Bee-Bot robot has been identified as one of the most suitable tools for introducing children to algorithmic thinking without the use of screens.

Bee-Bot is a didactic, play-based educational tool designed for integrated learning. It is shaped like a bee and equipped with buttons on its back through which commands controlling its movement are programmed. Bee-Bot can move forward, backward, left, and right in 15 cm sequences, rotate at 90-degree angles, and emit sound and light signals during movement. It is capable of storing up to forty programmed instructions (Zlatarović et al., 2022). Alongside Bee-Bot, educational mats are most commonly used. These mats represent structured or thematic surfaces divided into squares along which the robot moves in predefined steps. The mats may contain various types of content, including mathematical concepts (numbers, shapes), language-related activities (letters, words), spatial tasks (maps, mazes), and thematic scenarios (traffic,

professions, seasons, etc.). They provide a visual context for tasks and encourage problem-solving through the robot's movement.

An important component of the didactic set consists of coding cards displaying basic commands (forward, backward, left, right, start, pause), which serve as visual support for children while planning the robot's movement. These cards enable learners to first "plan the algorithm" on paper or on the table before entering it into Bee-Bot, thereby fostering an understanding of sequential programming.

Supplementary materials include various accessories and thematic sets, such as shells that adapt the robot to a specific topic or character, additional mats designed for particular educational content, and task or movement scenario cards. "Do-it-yourself" (DIY) materials created by teachers and children are also frequently used, allowing activities to be tailored to specific educational objectives.

Numerous studies indicate that the use of Bee-Bot directly stimulates the development of executive functions (EF), including working memory, inhibitory control, and cognitive flexibility (Di Lieto et al., 2020). The process of planning a sequence of commands requires children to anticipate the robot's movement, retain instructions in memory, and adapt their strategy through debugging in the event of errors. In addition, working with this robot enhances spatial orientation, understanding of directions (left, right, forward, backward), and mathematical skills, given that each movement step is precisely defined. Research also highlights the importance of collaborative learning, as working with the robot in small groups encourages communication, teamwork, and socio-emotional development (Zemzami & Zbat, 2025).

Teachers' Competencies and Attitudes

The implementation of educational robotics in early childhood education requires preschool teachers to possess a developed set of pedagogical, digital, and didactic competencies, as well as positive professional attitudes toward innovations in educational practice. Research indicates that the integration of robotics into work with young children becomes effective only when teachers are prepared to move beyond the traditional role of "knowledge transmitters" and assume the role of learning facilitators and designers of interactive learning environments (Papadakis et al., 2021).

The level of teachers' competencies for implementing educational robotics is most commonly examined through dimensions such as digital literacy, self-efficacy, pedagogical readiness, and experience in working with contemporary digital technologies. In a systematic analysis of programs and outcomes related to the use of educational robotics with young children, Trapero-González et al. (2025) identified several key competencies necessary for the successful implementation of digital tools in educational practice. These include digital competencies, encompassing basic knowledge of digital tools and programmable devices; didactic competencies, necessary for the effective integration of educational robotics into existing educational content; creative-pedagogical competencies, essential for designing play-based activities, mats, and learning scenarios; and reflective practice competencies, which enable teachers to critically evaluate and reflect upon their own practice.

The development of these competencies is influenced by numerous factors, among which the following are particularly significant: training in the use of educational robots, age and years of professional experience (which are often inversely related to technological openness and readiness to integrate digital tools into practice), previous experience with digital technologies, and positive perceptions regarding the usefulness of educational robotics for achieving educational outcomes. Research therefore demonstrates that both teachers' competencies and their attitudes toward educational robotics are statistically significantly associated with their knowledge of robotics and digital technologies, with higher levels of knowledge correlating with greater willingness to implement educational robotics in practice (Papadakis et al., 2021).

Research findings further indicate that these competencies are generally unevenly developed among preschool teachers, and often insufficiently systematized, representing one of the major barriers to the broader implementation of educational robotics in early childhood education.

A considerable proportion of teachers are only occasionally involved in activities related to educational robotics, while a smaller percentage have undergone intensive training or acquired systematic experience in this field. Moreover, most teachers tend to assess their own knowledge as insufficiently developed for the continuous application of robotics in practice (García-Fuentes et al., 2025). In addition, the lack of methodological preparation, insufficient technical support, and inadequate infrastructure have been identified as significant barriers to the wider use of educational robots in preschool education settings (Balint-Svella & Zsoldos Marchiş, 2022).

Considering that preschool teachers are intrinsically motivated toward professional development, yet often experience uncertainty due to rapid technological changes and increasing demands for mastering and implementing new pedagogical strategies, continuous professional development and institutional support are regarded as essential prerequisites for transforming teachers into leaders of digital innovation in early childhood education settings (Foti, 2021).

Methods

Research Subject and Aim

Based on the presented theoretical perspectives regarding the importance of educational robotics in early childhood education, as well as the role of preschool teachers in its implementation, there is a clear need for empirical investigation of these aspects in practice. In particular, it is important to examine the extent to which preschool teachers are prepared to implement the Bee-Bot robot in educational activities, as well as how they assess their own competencies in this field.

In this context, the subject of the present study concerns preschool teachers' attitudes and competencies related to the implementation of educational robotics in kindergarten settings.

The aim of the study is to examine the prevalence, modes of application, and pedagogical effects of using the Bee-Bot robot in educational work with preschool children in the Republic of Serbia, as well as to identify preschool teachers' attitudes and competencies regarding the implementation of educational robotics.

The implementation of the Bee-Bot robot in Serbian preschool institutions is still in its developmental phase and is not equally represented across all kindergartens. In certain institutions, particularly those participating in projects focused on digitalization and quality improvement, Bee-Bot is used as a tool for introducing children to the fundamentals of programming through play-based activities. The intention of the researchers was to identify the factors that facilitate or hinder the implementation of such innovations in early childhood education, in order to provide guidelines for improving teachers' professional development and the digitalization of educational practice in preschool settings.

Research description

The study was conducted using a descriptive method, with the aim of examining the attitudes and competencies of preschool teachers regarding the application of the Bee-Bot educational robot in preschool institutions in the Republic of Serbia. The starting point of the research is based on determining the level of teachers' familiarity with the Bee-Bot robot, the frequency and manner of its use in educational practice, as well as the assessment of the contribution of this technology to the development of various areas of child development.

The research also covers the professional competencies of teachers, their need for additional professional training, as well as the factors that limit the broader application of educational robotics in kindergartens. Special attention is given to teachers' attitudes toward the importance of integrating robotics into the contemporary preschool curriculum, as well as examining the relationship between prior professional training and the frequency of Bee-Bot use in practice.

Research Design and Variables

The research design includes the following variables: independent variables (years of work experience, level of education, prior training in the field of digital technologies, and availability of equipment in the institution) and dependent variables (frequency of Bee-Bot use, teachers' attitudes, assessment of children's developed competencies, and readiness for further application).

Based on theoretical knowledge and previous research in the field of educational robotics in early childhood education, it is assumed that the application of the Bee-Bot robot contributes to the improvement of learning through play and exploratory activities in the preschool context. It is also expected that teachers who have undergone appropriate training in digital technologies use Bee-Bot more frequently in their work, and that there is a statistically significant relationship between years of work experience and readiness to apply educational robotics. It is further assumed that teachers perceive Bee-Bot as contributing most to the development of logical thinking and spatial orientation in children, while lack of equipment and professional support is identified as a key barrier to its wider implementation in kindergartens. Finally, it is expected that teachers have predominantly positive attitudes toward the introduction of educational robotics in the modern preschool curriculum.

Participants and Data Analysis

The study involved one hundred (N=100) preschool teachers employed in preschool institutions in several cities in the Republic of Serbia, using a random sampling method. Data were collected through a survey technique, using a structured questionnaire that included Likert-scale items, multiple-choice questions, and one open-ended question. The questionnaire was developed for the purposes of this research and distributed electronically via Google Forms. Participation in the study was voluntary and anonymous, and respondents were informed about the purpose of the study and the use of the collected data prior to completing the questionnaire.

Data analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential statistical procedures, including frequency analysis, arithmetic mean and standard deviation, χ^2 test, as well as correlation analysis.

Results

The study sample consisted of a total of 100 (N=100) respondents employed in preschool institutions in Serbia. Regarding gender distribution, the sample was predominantly composed of female participants (N = 96; 96.0%), while male respondents were significantly less represented (N = 4; 4.0%). Such a sample structure was expected, given that the preschool teaching profession is traditionally female-dominated.

The average number of years of work experience among respondents was $M = 14.63$ years ($SD=10.17$), with a range from 1 to 40 years of professional experience. The median work experience was 15 years, indicating a relatively balanced representation of participants with both lower and higher levels of professional experience.

Regarding educational attainment, the majority of respondents held bachelor's-level vocational or academic degrees (N=57; 57%), while a significant proportion had completed master's or specialist studies (N = 39; 39%). A small number of respondents had completed secondary education (N = 4; 4.0%). These findings indicate a relatively high overall level of formal education among the participants.

Analysis of responses related to familiarity with the Bee-Bot robot shows that the largest proportion of respondents are familiar with and actively use Bee-Bot in their work with children (N=59; 59%). A considerable number of preschool teachers reported being familiar with the robot but not using it in practice (N=35; 35%), while a small number stated that they were not familiar with the Bee-Bot robot (N=7; 7%). These results suggest that educational robotics is present in a certain number of preschool institutions, although its application is still not uniformly distributed.

Regarding professional training in the field of educational robotics and digital technologies, the results show that 47 respondents (47%) had attended some form of training related to the use of

Bee-Bot or other educational robots, while more than half of the sample (N=54; 54%) had not received such professional development. These findings indicate a need for further organization of professional training programs and strengthening of preschool teachers' competencies for the application of educational robotics in early childhood education settings.

The results indicate predominantly positive attitudes of preschool teachers toward the use of educational robotics in early childhood education. The statement regarding the importance of educational robotics in preschool settings received a high mean score (M=4.33; SD = 0.66), suggesting that respondents largely recognize the potential of modern digital technologies in working with preschool children. Teachers rated their own digital competencies as moderately developed (M=3.40; SD=1.35). The relatively high standard deviation indicates considerable heterogeneity in responses, reflecting pronounced individual differences in perceived levels of digital competence among respondents.

Further analysis shows that professional development is a significant factor in the frequency of Bee-Bot use in educational practice. A statistically significant difference was found between teachers who had attended digital technology training and those who had not, with trained teachers using Bee-Bot more frequently in their work with children (Mann-Whitney U=602.00, $p < 0.001$). This finding confirms the importance of continuous professional development and indicates that additional training contributes to greater confidence and readiness for the application of educational robotics in practice.

Regarding the correlation between years of work experience and readiness to apply educational robotics, the results of the correlation analysis did not show a statistically significant association between these variables ($r_s = -0.07$; $p = 0.462$). Although a weak negative correlation was observed, it was not statistically significant, indicating that readiness to use the Bee-Bot robot does not depend on teachers' length of professional experience. This finding may be explained by the fact that interest in digital technologies is not necessarily determined by years of service, but rather by individual motivation, access to training, and working conditions within institutions.

The analysis of teachers' responses shows that Bee-Bot is most commonly associated with the development of spatial orientation (56%), logical thinking (48%), and early mathematical concepts in children (40%), while problem-solving, sequential thinking, and collaborative learning were also frequently mentioned. These findings support theoretical assumptions that educational robotics contributes to the development of elements of computational thinking and promotes active learning through play, exploration, and manipulation of concrete materials.

The study also identified certain barriers to the broader and more frequent use of the Bee-Bot robot in preschool settings. The main obstacles include an insufficient number of robots and mats (34%), lack of time during the working day (33%), and the need for additional professional training (23%), while other factors were mentioned to a lesser extent (1–3%). These findings indicate that the successful integration of educational robotics depends not only on teachers' positive attitudes, but also on institutional and material conditions that enable its sustainable implementation in practice.

Overall, the results confirm that preschool teachers recognize the educational value of the Bee-Bot robot and its potential to foster exploratory, problem-based, and collaborative learning in early childhood education. At the same time, the findings highlight the need for systematic professional development, improved digital equipment in preschool institutions, and stronger institutional support for the implementation of educational robotics in everyday educational practice.

Discussion

Results indicate that preschool teachers largely recognize the importance of educational robotics in contemporary preschool education and evaluate the Bee-Bot robot as a stimulating tool for the development of various aspects of children's learning and development. The findings confirm theoretical assumptions according to which educational robotics contributes to active, experiential, and exploratory learning, in which the child takes an active role in problem-solving, planning, and exploration.

The results show that respondents have predominantly positive attitudes toward the use of educational robotics in preschool settings, which is confirmed by high mean scores on items related to the importance of the Bee-Bot robot in working with children. These findings are consistent with the research of Papadakis et al. (2021), who emphasize that preschool teachers recognize the potential of educational robotics for the development of creativity, collaboration, and problem-solving skills in preschool children. Similar results are reported by Negrini (2020), whose study shows that teachers perceive educational robotics as an important tool for the development of transversal competencies and contemporary learning skills. The obtained results may be explained by the fact that Bee-Bot enables learning through play, manipulation, and exploration, which aligns with the developmental characteristics of preschool-aged children.

A particularly important finding concerns the statistically significant correlation between professional training and the frequency of Bee-Bot use in practice. This result confirms the assumption that professional development and additional training play an important role in the development of teachers' competencies for the application of modern technologies in practice. These findings are consistent with the study by Schina et al. (2021), which shows that training in educational robotics significantly contributes to greater self-confidence, more positive attitudes, and increased readiness of teachers to use robots in educational processes. The authors emphasize that hands-on experience with robots reduces uncertainty and increases perceived usefulness of educational robotics, which is also confirmed by the findings of this study.

On the other hand, the results did not confirm a statistically significant relationship between years of work experience and readiness to apply educational robotics. Although a weak negative correlation was observed, it did not reach statistical significance. This finding suggests that openness to innovation and readiness to use digital technologies are not necessarily dependent on teachers' professional experience. Similar findings are reported by Negrini (2020), who states that age and length of service are not decisive factors in forming positive attitudes toward educational robotics, but that motivation, prior experience, and availability of professional support play a more important role. These results may also be interpreted in the context of contemporary educational changes, where digital competencies have become an integral part of the professional role of preschool teachers, regardless of years of experience.

Regarding the perceived developmental potential of the Bee-Bot robot, teachers most frequently highlighted its contribution to the development of logical thinking, spatial orientation, problem-solving, and basic mathematical concepts. These findings are consistent with research indicating that educational robotics contributes to the development of elements of computational thinking, sequential planning, and problem-solving abilities in young children. In their study on teachers' perceptions of educational robotics, Chevalier et al. (2022) emphasize that robotics-based activities foster the development of computational thinking, creative problem-solving, and collaborative learning, which aligns with the perceptions of teachers in this study. Additionally, research on STEM activities using the Bee-Bot robot in preschool education shows that children develop an exploratory approach, critical thinking, and teamwork skills through interaction with the robot.

Although teachers' attitudes toward educational robotics are generally positive, the results also indicate certain barriers to its wider implementation in practice. The most significant barriers identified include lack of equipment, a limited number of Bee-Bot robots, insufficient time for activity planning, and the need for additional training and professional support. Similar issues have been identified in previous studies, which emphasize that successful integration of educational robotics depends not only on teachers' attitudes but also on material conditions, institutional support, and access to continuous professional development.

Overall, the findings confirm that the Bee-Bot robot represents a significant didactic resource in preschool education and that teachers recognize its potential for promoting active, exploratory, and collaborative learning. At the same time, the results highlight the need for systematic improvement of teachers' competencies, organization of professional training, and provision of adequate material and technical conditions in order for educational robotics to become a sustainable and well-integrated part of contemporary preschool practice.

Limitations of the Study

Although the study provides important insights into preschool teachers' attitudes and experiences regarding the use of the Bee-Bot robot in preschool education, certain limitations should be acknowledged, as they may affect the interpretation of the findings.

First, a key limitation relates to the sample size and structure. The study was conducted on a sample of 100 respondents, with a predominant representation of female participants, which reflects the gender structure of the preschool teaching profession. However, this also limits the possibility of comparing results across gender. In addition, the sample was not evenly stratified by region or type of institution; therefore, the results should be interpreted with caution when generalizing to the broader population of preschool teachers.

Another important limitation concerns the use of self-reported data. Attitudes, competency assessments, and reported frequency of Bee-Bot use are based on participants' subjective responses, which may lead to social desirability bias and discrepancies between perceived and actual levels of educational robotics use in practice.

Furthermore, the study was cross-sectional in design, meaning that data were collected at a single point in time. As a result, it is not possible to establish causal relationships between the examined variables. The findings can therefore only be interpreted in terms of observed associations and group differences.

An additional limitation is the uneven level of prior experience with educational robotics among respondents. Some preschool teachers had previous training and experience with the Bee-Bot robot, while others had no direct exposure to educational robotics, which may have influenced their attitudes and perceptions of its applicability.

Moreover, the study did not include direct observation of educational practice or assessment of the effects of Bee-Bot use on children's outcomes, but focused exclusively on teachers' perspectives. Future research could incorporate mixed-method approaches, classroom observations, as well as evaluations of children's competencies through experimental or longitudinal designs.

Despite these limitations, the study makes a meaningful contribution to understanding preschool teachers' attitudes and competencies related to educational robotics and may serve as a foundation for further research and improvements in early childhood education practice.

Conclusions

The contemporary preschool curriculum increasingly recognizes the importance of integrating digital technologies and innovative learning approaches that promote the child's active role in the process of exploration and knowledge construction. In this context, educational robotics, particularly the Bee-Bot robot, represents a significant didactic resource that enables the integration of play, exploration, and the development of various cognitive and social competencies in preschool children.

The results of this study indicate that preschool teachers recognize the potential of the Bee-Bot robot for fostering logical thinking, spatial orientation, problem-solving, and collaborative learning, and that they express predominantly positive attitudes toward its use in educational practice. At the same time, the findings show that successful integration of educational robotics requires continuous professional development of teachers, adequate material and technical support, and the creation of a supportive institutional environment. Although educational robotics is not yet fully implemented in the everyday practice of all preschool institutions, it is evident that its application opens new opportunities for the development of contemporary competencies in children through experiential, exploratory, and problem-based learning. Therefore, it can be expected that educational robots will play an increasingly important role in shaping stimulating learning environments in early childhood education in the future.

The obtained findings may serve as a starting point for further research in the field of educational robotics, as well as contribute to the improvement of preschool teachers' professional practice and the development of modern approaches to learning in early childhood education.

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PRIMENA BEEBOT ROBOTA U VASPITNO-OBRAZOVNOM RADU U PREDŠKOLSKIM USTANOVAMA U SRBIJI

Ivan Tomić i Katarina Tomić

Akademija vaspitačko medicinskih strukovnih studija Kruševac

Apstrakt

U savremenom predškolskom obrazovanju sve veći značaj pridaje se integraciji digitalnih tehnologija u vaspitno-obrazovni rad, posebno u funkciji podsticanja ranog razvoja logičkog mišljenja, rešavanja problema i osnovnih koncepata programiranja. Jedan od alata koji se sve češće koristi u ovom kontekstu jeste edukativni robot Bee-Bot, koji omogućava deci da kroz igru usvajaju elementarne principe sekvenciranja i algoritamskog razmišljanja. Uvođenje digitalnih sredstava u predškolske ustanove zahteva i ispitivanje stavova i iskustava vaspitača u vezi sa integracijom digitalnih sredstava u vaspitno-obrazovni proces, njihovom pedagoškom vrednošću, kao i izazovima i ograničenjima njihove primene u radu sa decom predškolskog uzrasta. Cilj istraživanja bio je da se ispita u kojoj meri i na koji način vaspitači u Srbiji primenjuju Bee-Bot u radu sa decom predškolskog uzrasta, kao i da se identifikuju oblasti dečjeg razvoja na koje njegova primena najviše utiče. Posebni ciljevi odnosili su se na ispitivanje učestalosti korišćenja, nivoa kompetencija vaspitača za primenu ovog alata, kao i percepcije njegovih pedagoških efekata. Istraživanje je sprovedeno kvantitativnim pristupom, tehnikom anketiranja. Instrument istraživanja bio je anketni upitnik konstruisan za potrebe rada i distribuiran ispitanicima preko opcije Google forms. Uzorak je obuhvatio 100 vaspitača iz različitih delova Srbije, odabranih metodom slučajnog uzorkovanja. Prikupljeni podaci analizirani su primenom deskriptivne statistike i odgovarajućih inferencijalnih postupaka. Rezultati istraživanja pokazuju da vaspitači prepoznaju značaj primene Bee-Bot robota u vaspitno-obrazovnom radu, posebno u razvoju kognitivnih sposobnosti, logičkog mišljenja i saradnje među decom. Procenjen je umeren nivo sopstvene digitalne kompetentnosti ($M=3,4$; $SD=1,35$), pri čemu visoka standardna devijacija ukazuje na izražene individualne razlike među ispitanicima. Utvrđena je statistički značajna razlika u učestalosti primene Bee-Bota između vaspitača koji su pohađali obuku i onih koji nisu ($Mann-Whitney U=602.00$, $p<.001$), pri čemu obučeni vaspitači značajno češće koriste ovaj alat. Ispitanici procenjuju da primena Bee-Bot-a najviše doprinosi razvoju prostorne orijentacije (56%), zatim logičkog mišljenja (48%) i usvajanju matematičkih pojmova (40%). Kao ključne prepreke za češću primenu izdvajaju se nedovoljan broj robota i podloga (34%), nedostatak vremena u radnom danu (33%) i potreba za dodatnom stručnom obukom (23%), dok su ostali faktori zastupljeni u manjoj meri (1–3%). Dobijeni nalazi ukazuju na potrebu unapređenja profesionalnog usavršavanja vaspitača i sistematičnije integracije digitalnih alata u predškolski kurikulum.

Ključne reči: Bee-Bot, predškolsko vaspitanje, digitalne tehnologije, vaspitači, rani razvoj, algoritamsko mišljenje